

CATALYTIC CONVERSION OF DIMETHYL ETHER TO ETHYLENE AND PROPYLENE

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Abstract. *In this work, the results on the creation of new high-performance catalytic systems modified with various elements are summarized. At the same time, the effect of the nature of the modifying element, as well as the high-temperature treatment with water vapor, on the texture, acidic characteristics and catalytic properties of the zeolite catalyst in the conversion of dimethyl ether to ethylene and propylene was considered. In order to increase the stability of the Mg-Zn-Zr-B-IOKL catalyst, it was proved that unmodified Mg-Zn-Zr-B-IOKL exhibited high activity when it was modified with P and Fe and used in the synthesis of ethylene and propylene from methanol and dimethyl ether. In the work, the catalytic conversion of dimethyl ether to ethylene and propylene was carried out in the Mg-Zn-Zr-B-IOKL catalyst under the following optimal conditions: ($T = 340^{\circ}\text{C}$, $R = 0.1 \text{ MPa}$, $\text{Var} = 1000\text{-}2000 \text{ h}^{-1}$. Raw material: DME (15%) ÷ N_2 (85%). In the case of modification of zirconium- and magnesium-containing zeolite catalysts with B, it was proved that in almost all cases, an increase in the selectivity for $\text{C}_2\text{-C}_4$ ethylene and propylene and a decrease in the amount of paraffins were observed. According to the obtained results, with an increase in zirconium concentration from 0.4 to 3.2 wt.%, there is an increase in the selectivity for $\text{C}_2\text{-C}_4$ ethylene and propylene from 42.1 to 74.5 wt.%. Paraffins are formed from 0.4 wt.% to 57 wt.% of zirconium. Thus, Mg-Zn-Zr-B-IOKL is an effective catalyst of methanol to ethylene and propylene, the addition of water to the raw material as a diluent significantly increases the activity of the catalyst and the yield of the target products and the time of stable operation of the catalyst are increased.*

Also, as a result of studying the textural and physicochemical characteristics of the catalyst by IR-spectroscopy, differential thermal analysis and thermogravimetry methods, it was proved that the treatment of zeolite with zirconium and boron compounds does not lead to the destruction of the zeolite structure.

Keywords: *dimethyl ether, methanol, ethylene, propylene, conversion, catalyst, synthesis, kinetic law.*

The aim of the work is to study the catalytic conversion of dimethyl ether to ethylene and propylene in the Mg-Zr-Zn-B-IOKL catalyst.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, methanol synthesis is carried out on Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃ catalyst at temperatures of 270-300°C under pressure of 5-10 MPa[1].

Ethylene and propylene are produced from methanol by two reactions:

The first method is based on obtaining ethylene and propylene by direct conversion of methyl alcohol in silicoaluminophosphate catalysts at temperatures of 450-550°C. The second method is based on obtaining ethylene and propylene in 99.6-99.8% purity and 70-90% yield in ZSM-5 type zeolites at temperatures of 430-550°C by dehydrating methanol, and propylene is produced more in this process [2-3].

Currently, processes for obtaining ethylene and propylene and polyethylene and polypropylene from methanol and dimethyl ether compete with the processes of naphtha pyrolysis and ethane cracking currently used in industry.

The development of this method is accelerated by the increase in demand for consumer products [4-5]. Today, the world production of ethylene and propylene is exceeded 280 mln. tons[6]. The demand for ethylene and propylene is especially high, they account for more than 96% of the total volume of production of unsaturated hydrocarbons [7-9], the volume of production capacity has doubled since the beginning of the century.

The most common catalysts in the synthesis of ethylene and propylene from dimethylene ether are high-silica zeolites of the ZSM type.

The influence on the properties of zeolite catalysts consists of modification with metal compounds[5-9], which leads to changes in their texture and acidic properties[10-12]. The effect of the nature of the modifying element on the properties of zeolite catalysts [13-17] has been widely studied, but until now, no unified theory has been developed to understand the role of the nature of the modifying element in the change of their catalytic properties [18-21]. A change in acidic properties can be achieved by pre-treatment of catalysts at high temperature or by changing the amount of water in the initial feedstock.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

High-silica zeolite with $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3=26$ mol ratio was used in the work[22-25]. Zirconium and zinc were added to the catalysts by means of ion exchange. Boron was introduced by absorbing granules obtained by extrusion from a mixture of zeolite with a binder.

Tests of catalyst samples in the conversion of dimethyl ether to ethylene and propylene were conducted in a microcatalytic flow device at a pressure of 0.1 MPa and a temperature range of 270-450°C. The flow rate of the initial gas mixture was changed in the range of 500-1500 h⁻¹, the concentration of dimethyl ether in the initial mixture was 10% by volume. Catalyst weight (0.5 g, 1 cm³), 2 cm³ quartz nozzles were loaded into the reactor. The catalytic conversion of methanol to ethylene and propylene was investigated on Mg-Zn-Zr-B/IOKII catalyst.

IR-spectroscopy, differential thermal analysis, and thermogravimetric methods were used to study the structural and textural characteristics of zirconium- and magnesium-retaining samples; also, the adsorption capacity of zeolite for benzene was measured by calculating the threshold values of adsorption using the Dubinin equation. The acidic properties of the catalysts were studied by the method of temperature-programmable desorption of ammonia.

Catalyst tests were conducted in a device with a flow-type reactor at a temperature of 320-380°C and atmospheric pressure. The volume of the catalyst was varied between 3 and 10 cm³.

To determine the topography of the sample surface, the powder was placed in a JEOL JSM6390A scanning electron microscope. A sample of the studied powder is placed on a carbon tape for analysis. Non-solid particles were removed from the tape surface. The elemental composition of the obtained products was determined using X-ray spectral microanalysis (RSMA) with a JEOL JED-2200 EDS attachment on a JEOL JSM6390A scanning electron microscope.

The phase composition of the synthesis products was determined using X-ray phase analysis (XPA). X-ray spectra were recorded on an ARL X'trA automated diffractometer (Thermo Scientific) using CuK α radiation at a 2-degree angle scanning from 10 degrees to 80 degrees at a rate of 2 degrees. The resulting spectra were processed using a custom WinXRD software package. The size of the crystallite was determined by the broadening of the interference line in the diffractogram.

The study of the porous structure of the sample was carried out using the temperature adsorption method of nitrogen on the ASAP-2010 device of Micromeritics. First, the sample was vacuumed to 0.4 Pa at a temperature of 350°C. N₂ adsorption was carried out at 77K.

Acidic properties were studied by the method of thermoprogrammed desorption of ammonia in a universal sorption gas analyzer USGA-101.

The qualitative and quantitative composition of the reaction products was analyzed by the chromatographic method in the "Crystal 5000" chromatograph with a capillary column and a flame-ionization detector. The amount of hydrogen and carbon oxides was determined on a "Crystal-5000" chromatograph equipped with a thermal conductivity detector and a PropakQ phase retention column.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

First, the effect of boron on the catalytic properties of zirconium- and magnesium-supported zeolite catalysts, which were previously developed for the conversion of dimethyl ether to ethylene and propylene, was investigated. When modifying these catalysts with boron, in almost all cases, an increase in the selectivity for C₂-C₄ ethylene and propylene and a decrease in the amount of paraffins were observed (Table 1). Modification of Zr-IOKII with magnesium leads to a significant increase in ethylene selectivity from 18.6 to 29.2 wt.%. The proportion of propylene and butenes in the Zr-Mg-IOKII catalyst is slightly higher than that of Mg-IOKII.

Table 1

Conversion of dimethyl ether to ethylene and propylene on zeolite catalysts

Catalyst	Selectivity, %			
	Ethylene and propylene			Paraffins C ₁₊
	C ₂	C ₃	$\sum C_2-C_3$	
IOKII	12,9	18,7	31.6	39,5
Zr-IOKII	18,6	32,3	50.9	28,4
Mg-IOKII	19,8	33,1	52.9	27,6
Mg-Zr-IOKII	29,2	34,4	63.6	25,9
Mg-Zr-Zn-IOKII	31,7	34,2	65.9	25,7
Mg-Zr-Zn-B-IOKII	32,5	35,2	67.7	19,7

Conditions: T = 340°C, R = 0.1 MPa, Var = 500-1500 h⁻¹. Conversion of dimethyl ether = 65-75%. Raw materials: DME (15%) ÷ N₂ (85%).

As can be seen from Table 1, in the presence of a Mg-IOKII catalyst, the selectivity to ethylene is 19.8%, the selectivity to propylene is 33.1%, and the selectivity to paraffins is 27.6%. In the presence of Mg-Zr-Zn-B-IOKII catalyst, selectivity to ethylene is 32.5%, selectivity to propylene is 35.2%, and selectivity to paraffins is 19.7%.

The modification of Zr-IOKI I and Zn-IOKI I samples with magnesium and boron led to a significant decrease in the total amount of acidic centers, and the zinc-retaining catalyst has a small amount of superacidic centers, unlike the zirconium-retaining catalyst (Table 2).

Table 2

Distribution of the amount of acidic centers according to the desorption activation energies of ammonia

Catalyst	Total amount of acidic centers, $\mu\text{mol/g}$	The amount of centers ($E < 130$ kJ/mol), $\mu\text{mol/g}$	The amount of centers ($130 < E < 180$ kJ/mol), $\mu\text{mol/g}$	The amount of centers ($E > 180$ kJ/mol li) $\mu\text{mol/g}$
IOKI I	700	275(36%)	485(64%)	-
IOKI I	880	340(38%)	540(61,3%)	5(0,7%)
Zr-IOKI I	700	275(35%)	455(65%)	-
Mg-IOKI I	680	340(50%)	335(49,3%)	5(0,7%)
Mg-Zr-IOKI I	630	340(54%)	290(46%)	-
Mg-Zr-Zn-IOKI I	450	260(58%)	180(40%)	10(2%)
Mg-Zr-Zn-B-IOKI I	445	220(49%)	165(37%)	60(13%)

The introduction of boron(B) into Mg-Zr-Zn-IOKI I also caused a decrease in the total acidity, a decrease in the percentage of medium-strength acidic centers, and a significant increase in the amount of superacidic centers.

Thus, the Mg-Zr-Zn-B-IOKI I catalyst is an effective catalyst for the synthesis of molecular ethylene and propylene from dimethyl ether, but the amount of isoparaffins in the liquid product is slightly lower than that of the Mg-Zr-IOKI I sample, which is due to the presence of superacidity.

By changing the contact time, a significant increase in the selectivity of gasoline hydrocarbon components was achieved up to 86 wt.%, but the percentage of isoparaffins decreased by 10%, and the amount of aromatic hydrocarbons increased by almost two times, while maintaining the high catalytic activity of the Mg-Zr-Zn-B-IOKI I system. It was 46.1% by mass (Table 3).

Table 3

Effect of contact time on activity and selectivity of Mg-Zr-Zn-B- IOKI I system

1/W, h	Conversion (%)	Selectivity, wt.%		Hydrocarbon content of the products, % mass				
		Gas	Selectivity to hydrocarbons, %	Iso-paraffins	Normal paraffins	Cyclo-paraffins	Aromatic-carbohydrates	Olefins
0,094	99,8	34,9	75,1	57,0	7,9	6,6	28,6	6,5
0,189	99,5	23,7	76,3	51,4	4,3	3,4	33,9	7,0
0,37	99,5	13,8	86,2	46,5	2,4	5,0	46,1	8,1

Oxidative regeneration of Mg-Zr-Zn-B-IOKI I catalyst at high temperature did not affect the activity of the catalyst. There was a slight increase in the selectivity of gasoline hydrocarbon components and a change in the distribution of hydrocarbon products: after regeneration, the amount of isoparaffins decreased from 57 to 43 wt.%, and the amount of aromatic hydrocarbons in liquid products increased sharply and was about 50 wt.% compared to the new sample.

In order to increase the stability of the Mg-Zn-Zr-B/IOKI I catalyst used in the synthesis of ethylene and propylene from methanol and dimethyl ether, various modifiers such as P and Fe

were added and experiments were conducted. As a result of the conducted experiments, it was proved that modification with P and Fe leads to a decrease in the yield of ethylene and propylene.

Thus, unmodified Mg-Zn-Zr-B/ЮКЦ show high activity, the decrease in catalyst activity over time, i.e., the decrease in the yield of ethylene and propylene formation, is due to the coking of the acid centers of the catalyst and the clogging of the thin pores and channels of the zeolite.

Figure 1. Dependence of ethylene and propylene yield on catalyst working time ($=1000 h^{-1}$, $T=340^{\circ}C$, $P=0.1 MPa$)

Figure 2. Conversion of dimethyl ether and methanol in Mg-Zn-Zr-B/ЮКЦ ($=1000 h^{-1}$, $T=340^{\circ}C$, $P=0.1 MPa$)

For some processes carried out on zeolite catalysts, the addition of water increases the catalyst residence time. In this regard, the effect of Mg-Zn-Zr-B/ЮКЦ catalytic water was investigated.

As can be seen in Table 4, the addition of water to the raw material slightly increases the yield of ethylene and propylene, but the working time of the catalyst increases by ≈ 2 times. In this case, the yield of ethylene is much higher than when pure methanol is used.

Table 3

Dependence of the yield of ethylene and propylene on the operating time of the catalyst based on Mg-Zn-Zr-B/IOKI in the presence and absence of water in the raw material (=1000 hours⁻¹, VMethanol=15 coat-1, T=340°C, P=0.1 MPa)

Catalyst operating time, hours	Methanol			Methanol + water		
	Ethylene	Propylene	Butenes	Ethylene	Propylene	Butenes
5	19,8	40,4	18,6	25,4	35,5	13,8
10	22,2	38,6	16,8	25,9	35,8	12,9
15	26,6	37,5	11,4	28,2	34,7	12,6
20	30,4	35,2	9,4	31,5	34,7	11,5
25	15,4	25,3	7,4	29,4	30,5	10,9
30	6,7	5,7	2,8	27,4	27,2	10,3
35	3,5	5,4	2,9	24,4	25,7	9,8
40	1,6	3,9	3,5	20,6	22,8	9,9

Because water molecules blocking strong acid centers prevent ethylene from turning into hydrocarbons of high molecular mass.

Thus, Mg-Zn-Zr-B/IOKI is an effective catalyst of methanol to ethylene and propylene, the addition of water to the raw material as a diluent significantly increases the activity of the catalyst and increases the yield of the target products and increases the stable working time of the catalyst.

Figure 3 shows the dependence of the conversion of dimethyl ether on the contact time ($1/\tau$), from which it can be seen that the activity of the catalytic system increases with the increase of $1/\tau$. At the same time, with the increase of dimethylether conversion, the selectivity for ethylene and C_2^+ paraffins partially increased, the selectivity for C_2-C_5 ethylene and propylene did not change. Because at this time, the oligomerization reaction rate of ethylene is lower than the hydrogenation reaction rate.

$T=340^\circ\text{C}$, $R = 0.1 \text{ MPa}$, $=1000 \text{ h}^{-1}$. Syre: 15% dimethyl ether +85% N_2

Figure 3. Dependence of the dimethyl ether conversion on the conditional contact time ($1/\tau$) in the Mg-Zr-Zn-B-IOKI catalyst

CONCLUSION

Thus, unmodified Mg-Zn-Zr-B/IOKI \square shows high activity, the decrease in catalyst activity over time, i.e., the decrease in the yield of ethylene and propylene formation, is explained by the coking of the acid centers of the catalyst and the clogging of the thin pores and channels of the zeolite. The addition of water to the raw material slightly increases the yield of ethylene and propylene, but the working time of the catalyst increases by ≈ 2 times. In this case, the yield of ethylene is much higher than when pure methanol is used. This is because water molecules blocking strong acid centers prevent ethylene from turning into high molecular weight hydrocarbons.

Based on the research, it can be seen that the zinc-modified IOKI \square catalyst is the most effective among the studied samples for obtaining ethylene and propylene from dimethyl ether. The introduction of zinc into the zeolite not only increases the total yield of C₂⁻-C₄⁻ ethylene and propylene, but also leads to a decrease in methane formation.

In conclusion, the Mg-Zr-Zn-B-IOKI \square sample is an effective catalyst for the synthesis of gasoline hydrocarbon components from dimethylether, but the amount of isoparaffins in the liquid product is slightly lower than that of the Mg-Zr-IOKI \square sample, which is due to the presence of superacidity.

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